

Ref. Ares(2024)3926210 - 31/05/2024
ENVIRONMENT PARK

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idea energy

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Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno

REGIONALNA IZBA GOSPODARCZA POMORZA

TWeD

BALKAN HYDROGEN CLUSTER

D 5.3

Communication and Dissemination Activities Report

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members.

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Clean Hydrogen Partnership. Neither the European Union nor the Clean Hydrogen Partnership can be held responsible for them.

www.hypop-project.eu

info@hypop-project.eu

#HYPOPPROJECT

D 5.3	Communication and Dissemination Activities Report
DELIVERABLE TYPE	Report
MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERABLE	M12, 31/05/2024
WORK PACKAGE	WP 5
LEADER	Lead Beneficiary
DISSEMINATION LEVEL	Public
AUTHORS	Valeria Mingardi Marco Regi Chiara Pocaterra Sara Silvi
PROGRAMME	HORIZON EUROPE
GRANT AGREEMENT	101111933
START	01/Jun/2023
DURATION	24 Months

Contributors

NAME	ORGANISATION
Valeria Mingardi	APRE
Marco Regi	APRE
Chiara Pocaterra	APRE
Sara Silvi	APRE

Peer Reviews

NAME	ORGANISATION
Marianna Franchino	ENVI
Ilaria Schiavi	ENVI

Revision History

VERSION	DATE	REVIEWER	COMMENTS
0.1	20/05/2024	Valeria Mingardi (APRE) Marco Regi (APRE), Sara Silvi (APRE), Chiara Pocaterra (APRE)	first draft
0.2	27/05/2024	Marianna Franchino (ENVI) Marco Regi (APRE) Valeria Mingardi (APRE)	Review of first draft version
0.3	28/05/2024	Valeria Mingardi (APRE) Marco Regi (APRE), Sara Silvi (APRE), Chiara Pocaterra (APRE)	Second review

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Deliverable abstract

The present document D5.3 "Communication and Dissemination Activities Report" is a Delivery of Work Package 5 – Communication, Dissemination & Exploitation.

This deliverable intends illustrates the 'Communication and Dissemination Activities performed from HYPOP's Partners during the first 12 months of the project. In particular:

- Workshop, Conference, Symposium (participation and organization)
- Stakeholders engagement
- Papers and Publication
- Public engagement and educational activities
- Social media, website news, newsletter
- etc.

Keywords

Hydrogen, engagement, , project communalities, communication and dissemination.

Index of Contents

1	Introduction	8
1.1.	Context and background	8
1.2.	Specific objectives, expected outcomes and impacts of project HYPOP	9
2	HYPOP Communication and Dissemination activities	11
2.1	HYPOP Project Partner Activities	13
2.1.1	Workshops, Conferences, Symposium.....	13
2.1.2	Fairs & Exhibitions:	23
2.1.3	Stakeholders Engagement Activities	24
2.1.4	Paper and publication.....	29
2.1.5	Public engagement and educational activities	30
2.1.6	Social media, website news, newsletter.....	32
2.2	KPI Monitoring.....	40
3	Conclusion	43
4	References	44

Index of Tables

Table 3	C&D project’s KPI	40
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Index of Figures

Figure 1	Glossary format post example	11
Figure 2	News format posts example	12
Figure 3	Events, H2 Project format posts examples	12
Figure 4	Webinar “WHat do Europeans know about hydrogen technologies?”	13
Figure 5	Fuel cells and Hydrogen event.....	14
Figure 6	Clean Hydrogen Partnership Info Call 2024	14
Figure 7	Conference: Energetab – Forum Profesjonalistów PSME.....	15
Figure 8	PCHET	16
Figure 9	Spotkanie Pomorskiej Platformy Rozwoju Morskiej Energetyki Wiatrowej	16
Figure 10	Wirtualna Rzeczywistość (VR) jako nowa forma kształcenia kompetencji przyszłość.....	17

Figure 11 Warsztaty konsultacyjne w zakresie rozwoju gospodarki wodorowej na Pomorzu.....	18
Figure 12 Offshore2Hydrogen	18
Figure 13 EduOffshoreWind	19
Figure 14 H2Poland.....	20
Figure 15 WEBINAR: INWESTYCJE WODOROWE – POTENCJAŁ A WYZWANIA.....	20
Figure 16 PESA SMART ENERGY FORUM ENEX	21
Figure 17 Spotkanie Online Zaawansowane Materiały dla Rozwoju Technologii Wodorowych.....	22
Figure 18 Spotkanie online: Kreowanie zrównoważonych rozwiązań dzięki synergii wodoru i zaawansowanych materiałów	22
Figure 19 Professional Meeting on Hydrogen – PMH2.....	23
Figure 20 POLLUTEC 2023	24
Figure 21 ENVI H2 DAY	24
Figure 22 ANIMA GET IDROGENO	25
Figure 23 HYVOLUTION PARIS	26
Figure 24 World Hydrogen Summit.....	26
Figure 25 isit at Cluster Tweed, meeting with European Public actors.....	27
Figure 26 Whats up in ... Alpin Region concerning hydrogen valleys.....	28
Figure 27 CLUSTER TWEED General Assembly	29
Figure 28 Powering Net Zero Week.....	30
Figure 29 FABBRICHE APERTE PIEMONTE 2023.....	30
Figure 30 EARTH DAY "Stati Generali con i Giovani per la Terra"	31
Figure 31 Example ENVI post on social media	33
Figure 32 Example IMI post on social media	34
Figure 33 Example IMI re-post on social media	34
Figure 34 ENVIPARK NEWSLETTER	35
Figure 35 CLUSTER TWEED newsltter	36

Partners short names

ENVI	Environment Park Torino Spa
IMI	Institute For Methods Innovation
IME	Fundacion IMDEA Energia
APRE	Agenzia per la Promozione della Ricerca Europea
CNH2	Centro Nacional Del Idrogeno
RIGP	Regionalna Izba Gospodarcza Pomorza
CLUSTER TWEED	Cluster Tweed
BH2C	Balkanski Vodoroden Klaster

Abbreviations

GA	Grant Agreement
CA	Consortium Agreement

Executive Summary

This document illustrates the Communication and Dissemination Activities performed by the HYPOP's Partners during the first 12 months.

Within the project, each HYPOP's Partner have specific activities in each Country, in order to progress with all WPs. These activities even support the Communication and Dissemination of the project, other than create a HYPOP Community itself:

- analysis of the different approaches in EU state members with the main focus on the HYPOP partners Countries (WP1 related)
- info by EU NCPs (energies, climates in particular) regarding related and similar activities
- public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technology (WP1, WP2 related)
- National and European Hydrogen Technologies roadmaps analysis (energy, transportation, automotive, etc.) (WP1 related)
- public opinion regarding H2 implementation in EU countries in terms of technology understanding and acceptance (WP1 related)
- co-creation and engagement approach (WP1, WP2 related and preliminary to WP3, WP4)
- networking and collaboration with other EU-funded (but also regional and national) projects and initiatives (WP1, WP2, WP5 related)
- to increase the uptake and replication potential of the project's outputs across Europe and beyond (WP1, WP2, WP5 related)
- attend conferences in the hydrogen sector to present results, guidelines and toolboxes developed through HYPOP (WP5 related)
- use of the social media to increase the citizen hydrogen technologies awareness and acceptance (WP5 related)

The above-mentioned activities are strictly linked with C&D activities included in this report and here summarised:

- Workshop, Conference, Symposium (participation and organization)
- Stakeholders engagement
- Papers and publication
- Public engagement and educational activities
- Social media, website news, newsletter
- Etc.

1 Introduction

1.1. Context and background

Project HYPOP - HYdrogen Public Opinion and accePtance, Grant Agreement nr 101111933 is a project supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members Hydrogen Europe and Hydrogen Europe Research, and co-funded by the European Union.

Project HYPOP's Overall Objective is to raise public awareness and trust towards hydrogen technologies and their systemic benefits, through:

- the preparation of guidelines and good practices that will help to define more effectively how citizens, consumers/end-users and stakeholders can be involved in the implementation of Hydrogen technologies
- the creation of a web platform, and social media, collecting communication material, mainly videos, on new hydrogen technologies, developed according to the early findings of the public engagement activities.

To reach the overall goals of the project, 2 different target groups will be targeted, engaged and involved directly in dedicated activities:

- the first target group brings together: citizens, consumers, end users and communication experts. The project will analyze the public understanding of citizens aged 15 and above in each of the Country or Region surveyed (Public Opinion Survey, commissioned by Hydrogen Europe in early 2022 and expected to be completed by spring 2023) with a deep focus on East EU areas (owing also to the involvement of local partners in Poland and Bulgaria).
- the second one includes the following stakeholders: First responders, permitting entities, certification bodies and decision makers.

Hydrogen is one of the key components of the energy decarbonization strategy of the Union. Its contribution is considered crucial within the main European Union Policies.

The development of Hydrogen technologies and their integration into the market energy can represent an important opportunity to face the challenge of climate neutrality and the energy crisis that Europe, its economy and its citizens are currently living through.

Public awareness activities are essential for increasing social acceptance and trust in hydrogen-based technologies throughout the European Union, particularly for addressing the potential lack of knowledge or mistrust of key stakeholders directly involved in the first phases of mass deployment in Europe.

This Plan for communication, dissemination and exploitation aims at outlining an adequate and impactful approach towards awareness raising and outreach, supporting thus strongly the engagement of relevant stakeholders in the project activity and preparing the ground for the use of its results.

1.2. Specific objectives, expected outcomes and impacts of project HYPOP

HYPOP will strive to achieve the following specific objectives:

- Understanding public perceptions and reactions to hydrogen and fuel cell technologies
- Identification of the main individual-level determinants of public understanding and acceptance of hydrogen technologies
- Enhancing involvement of citizens in the implementation of solutions contributing to the transition to hydrogen and fuel cells
- Understanding the pathways to influence public opinion by analysis of the current depiction of hydrogen technologies in broadcasts, newspapers, and social media, and from this developing a public information strategy
- Assessment of the specific role of the socio-economic and environmental impacts of hydrogen technologies
- Clear guidance on safety and certification and support to obtain permits and authorisations for installing hydrogen technologies
- Engagement on Hydrogen Technologies' implementation
- Identifying the safety approaches and the safety barriers in a range of different Countries, in order to create a map of the main requirements (certification) for installing hydrogen technologies and facilities
- Identifying the attitudes of the different countries towards social life cycle assessment (S-LCA) of the hydrogen technologies

Through its different operational activities, HYPOP will aim to achieve the objectives mentioned above, whilst the transversal work of “impact maximisation”, which includes communication and dissemination, will act in support: the aim being to **leverage results and bring them to an upper level, reaching the widest possible audience of relevant stakeholders and engaging them into the project activities (in line with the stakeholder engagement strategy of the project) and the exploitation of results.**

Below the main project outcomes and expected impacts:

- Outcomes:
 - Reach a deeper comprehension of the public opinion on hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the social awareness, trust and reduction of the social distance to the hydrogen topic
 - Improvement of the understanding of the hydrogen technologies
 - Improvement of the scientific community and stakeholders' awareness of the public opinion on hydrogen topic, limits and possible drivers into the acceptance process
- Impacts:
 - Socio-cultural (increase the knowledge and acceptance)
 - Environmental/Climatic (hydrogen is a valid energy carrier used to produce clean energy with environment benefits)
 - Scientific (create more efficient technologies to integrate into the market)

- Political (improvement and acceptance of the energy strategy proposed to address the challenges of reaching climate neutrality and mitigating the energy crisis in Europe)
- Economic (long-term benefits in terms of infrastructure, and energy supply at small and large scale).

2 HYPOP Communication and Dissemination activities

The present chapter summarises the Communication and Dissemination activities performed within HYPOP Project Year 1 (M1-M12).

C&D activities have been performed by using the project branding and toolkit prepared at the beginning of the project (see D5.2 – Visual Identity Handbook). Awareness campaigns have been tailored for the social media HYPOP project profiles (LinkedIn, X, Instagram, Facebook). Indeed, website and social media represent together the main project’s communication channels.

APRE, as WP5 leader, took care of preparing graphic materials and contents for the campaigns, taking advantages of partners’ skills and expertise into the hydrogen topic. An interactive discussion and engagement activities was also performed during the last HYPOP General Assembly in November 2023 (M6), in order to collect information and suggestions by all partners and define the awareness campaigns. The activity led to the identification of 6 original formats on: **Glossary, Partner presentations, Hydrogen news, Hydrogen events, Hydrogen projects and opportunities for funding** (Figure 1, Figure 2Figure 3).

The Glossary format is specifically meant to introduce some simple key words related to hydrogen topic, decarbonisation, renewable energy or sustainability in general. This approach allows to start a first step of community engagement. Examples coming from X Platform – but shared in all social media accounts – are here reported to give evidence of the work done:

Figure 1 Glossary format post example

Figure 2 News format posts example

Figure 3 Events, H2 Project format posts examples

To guarantee a constant and monitored communication through the project’s channels, a specific Editorial Plan (example in **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**, **Errore. L'origine riferimento non è stata trovata.**) was prepared by APRE and shared among the Consortium (refers to D5.1 First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan).

To support the C&D activities monitoring, APRE (WP5 leader) has prepared a Tracking File shared within the Consortium in the dedicated SharePoint. The Partners’ Activities are tracked monthly by type of activity, place and date, type of stakeholders reached and project’s KPI monitored. In the following chapter, the tracked activities are reported.

Activities are classified by HYPOP Partner and type of action:

- Workshop, Conference, Symposium (participation and organization)
- Stakeholders engagement
- Papers and publication
- Public engagement and educational activities
- Social media, website news, newsletter

2.1 HYPOP Project Partner Activities

2.1.1 Workshops, Conferences, Symposium

#1

Title: *What do Europeans know about hydrogen technologies?*

Date: 7 July 2023

Location *On line*

Participation and/or organization: *Organized by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership JU*

Type of Action: *HYPOP Project presentation and Call to Action to collaborate*

Partner: ENVI

Web link: <https://www.clean-hydrogen.europa.eu/media/news/webinar-what-do-europeans-know-about-hydrogen-technologies-state-play-public-awareness-acceptance-2023-06-21-en>

Figure 4 Webinar "What do Europeans know about hydrogen technologies?"

#2

Title: *Fuel cells and Hydrogen, Observatory Relaunch*

Date: 29 september 2023

Location *On line*

Participation and/or organization: *Organized by European Hydrogen Observatory*

Type of Action: *Attendance*

Partner : APRE

Figure 5 Fuel cells and Hydrogen event

#3

Title: *Clean Hydrogen Partnership Info Day Call 2024 -*

Date: *26 January 2024*

Location *On line*

Participation and/or organization: *Organized by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership JU*

Type of Action: *Attendance*

Partner: *APRE*

Figure 6 Clean Hydrogen Partnership Info Call 2024

#4

Title: *Clean Hydrogen Partnership JU - Giornata Nazionale di Lancio del Bando 2024*

Date: *8 February 2024*

Location: *Roma*

Participation and/or organization: *: Clean Hydrogen Partnership JU, H2IT, ENEA*

Type of Action: *Attendance*

Partner: *APRE*

#5

Title: *HyVOLUTION PARIS 2024*

Date: *February 2024*

Location: *Paris (France)*

Participation and/or organization: *GreenTech+*

Type of Action. *ENVI there promoting h2 project, including HYPOP*

Partner: *ENVI*

Web link: <https://paris.hyvolution.com/en>

#6

Title: *Conference: Energetab – Forum Profesjonalistów PSME*

Date: 13.09.2023

Location: *Bielskobiata*

Participation and/or organization: Energetab

Type of action: RIGP and its activities *presentation*

Partner: RIGP

Web link:

<https://psme.org.pl/ogromny-sukces-forum-profesjonalistow-psme-podczas-energetab-2023-w-bielsku-bialej/>

O PSME ▾ CZŁONKOWIE ▾ AKTUALNOŚCI WYDARZENIA PLIKI DO POBRANIA KONTAKT

AKTUALNOŚCI

Ogromny sukces FORUM PROFESJONALISTÓW PSME podczas ENERGETAB 2023 w Bielsku Białej

24 PAŹDZIERNIKA 2023 PISZE: MARCIN_P

Na zaproszenie ZIAD Bielsko-Biała – organizatora targów Energetab zorganizowaliśmy podczas tegorocznej edycji targów bielskich dwudniowe wydarzenie: MAGAZYNY ENERGII – FORUM PROFESJONALISTÓW PSME.

Figure 7 Conference: Energetab – Forum Profesjonalistów PSME

#7

Title: *PCHET*

Date: 4-5.10.2023

Location: *Gdynia*

Participation and/or organization: PCHET

Type of action: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://pchet.klasterwodorowy.pl/>

Figure 8 PCHET

#8

Title: *Spotkanie Pomorskiej Platformy Rozwoju Morskiej Energetyki Wiatrowej (Meeting of the Pomeranian Platform for the Development of Offshore Wind Energy)*

Date: 1.12.2023

Location: *Gdańsk UMWP*

Participation and/or organization:

Type of action: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://pracodawcypomorza.pl/2023/12/07/chca-laczyc-offshore-z-wodorem/>

Pracodawcy Pomorza O NAS | STRUKTURA | DZIAŁALNOŚĆ | DOŁĄCZ DO NAS | INFORMACJE DLA CZŁONKÓW | KONTAKT | EN

JESTEŚ TUTAJ CHCĄ ŁĄCZYĆ OFFSHORE Z WODOREM

CZWARTEK 07-12-2023

Chcą łączyć offshore z wodorem

Powstała z inicjatywy Pomorskiego Urzędu Marszałkowskiego Platforma Offshore była współorganizatorem spotkania pt.: „Offshore i wodór w synergii dla rozwoju zielonej energetyki”, które odbyło się w Sali Okrągłej Urzędu Marszałkowskiego na początku grudnia br. Powstanie wodorowy euroklaster – zapewniał Marek Przeor z Komisji Europejskiej

Otwarcia spotkania dokonali: Leszek Bonna – wicemarszałek województwa pomorskiego; Sławomir Halbryt – prezydent RIGP Klaster Technologii Wodorowych, oraz dr Karolina Lipińska – architektka innowacji, (Urząd Marszałkowski Województwa Pomorskiego), prowadząca spotkanie.

W pierwszej części obrad skupiono się na aspektach rozwoju energetyki wiatrowej na morzu, w drugiej możliwości powiązania energii wytwarzanej przez morskie wiatraki z produkcją zielonego wodoru. Jak wiadomo, produkcja wodoru metodą elektrolizy wymaga zaangażowania dużej ilości energii, mogłaby ona pochodzić z działalności elektrowni wiatrowych na morzu.

Przyimiarki władz województwa pomorskiego

Pomorskie na lekkim gazie, czyli scenariusze pozyskiwania wodoru w kontekście sektora morskich farm wiatrowych omówił Artur Gosk z Referatu Planowania Energetycznego Urzędu Marszałkowskiego Województwa Pomorskiego.

Poinformował, że władze pomorskiego samorządu z dużym zaangażowaniem podeszły do tego zagadnienia tworząc Platformę Energetyki Wiatrowej. W Polsce działa już 15 Dolin Wodorowych, w tym dwie w naszym województwie: Pomorska Dolina Wodorowa (od 2018 roku) i Bursztynowa Dolina Wodorowa (od 2023 roku, powiązana przede wszystkim z Portem Gdynia). Celem działań jest, aby w 2040 roku dzięki współpracy lokalnych interesariuszy w woj. pom. funkcjonowała rozwinięta gospodarka wodorowa, oparta na zielonym wodrze, produkowanym na Pomorzu głównie na potrzeby strategicznych sektorów gospodarki regionu. **W opracowaniu koncepcji działań uczestniczyło 60 interesariuszy, w tym 37 podmiotów gospodarczych, np. Port Gdynia S.A., Gaz-System S.A., Rafineria Gdańska, Orlen S.A., Secescor S.A., a także Centrum Technologii Wodorowych powstałe na Politechnice Gdańskiej.**

Figure 9 Spotkanie Pomorskiej Platformy Rozwoju Morskiej Energetyki Wiatrowej

#9

Title: *Wirtualna Rzeczywistość (VR) jako nowa forma kształcenia kompetencji przyszłość (Virtual Reality (VR) as a new form of competence education future)*

Date: 5.12.2023

Location: Gdańsk

Participation and/or organization:

Type of action: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://app.evenuea.pl/event/xman-event/>

Figure 10 *Wirtualna Rzeczywistość (VR) jako nowa forma kształcenia kompetencji przyszłość*

#10

Title: *Warsztaty konsultacyjne w zakresie rozwoju gospodarki wodorowej na Pomorzu (Consultative workshops on the development of the hydrogen economy in Pomerania)*

Date: 26.09.2023

Location: Gdańsk

Participation and/or organization:

Type of action: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://app.evenuea.pl/event/warsztaty-konsultacyjne/>

Warsztaty konsultacyjne w zakresie rozwoju gospodarki wodorowej na Pomorzu

26 Września 2023, 10:00 (Wtorek) - 27 Września 2023, 15:00 (środa)

To wydarzenie już się skończyło. Zapraszamy na inne ciekawe wydarzenia.

Zapraszamy do udziału w warsztatach konsultacyjnych, które mają na celu przedyskutowanie z wybranymi przedstawicielami przedsiębiorstw i instytucji z regionu pomorskiego efektów projektu "Pomorskie na lekkim gazie - kierunki i scenariusze rozwoju gospodarki wodorowej do 2030 z perspektywą do 2040" przed ich upublicznieniem.

MIEJSCE

O4 Coworking
Al. Grunwaldzka 472, Gdańsk

Zobacz na mapie

Figure 11 Warsztaty konsultacyjne w zakresie rozwoju gospodarki wodorowej na Pomorzu

#11

Title: *Offshore2Hydrogen*

Date: 11.01.2024

Location: *Gdańsk*

Participation and/or organization:

Type of action *Organization & Participation - presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://app.evenea.pl/event/warsztaty-konsultacyjne/>

Grupa robocza Offshore2Hydrogen

11 Stycznia 2024, 10:00 (Czwartek)
Politechnika Gdańska, Gdańsk

To wydarzenie już się skończyło. Zapraszamy na inne ciekawe wydarzenia.

Celem grupy roboczej jest rozpoczęcie dialogu dotyczącego synergii sektora wodoru i polskiego offshore wind. Podczas grudniowego spotkania *sygnatariuszy Pomorskiej Platformy Rozwoju Morskiej Energetyki Wiatrowej na Bałtyku* zostaną przedstawione założenia, ogłoszony zostanie nabór do Grupy oraz termin pierwszego posiedzenia Grupy Roboczej Offshore2Hydrogen. Jej inicjatorem i koordynatorem jest *Klaster Technologii Wodorowych*.

SPOTKANIE ODBĘDZIE SIĘ 11 STYCZNIA O GODZ. 10:00 NA POLITECHNICIE GDAŃSKIEJ.

ZAPISY TRWAJĄ DO 8 STYCZNIA!

Celem dyskusji jest wypracowanie podstawowych ram regulacyjnych oraz założeń pozwalających na produkcję wodoru z morskich farm wiatrowych w Polsce.

MIEJSCE

Politechnika Gdańska
ul. Narutowicza 11/12, Gdańsk

Zobacz na mapie

TERMIN

Początek: 11 Stycznia 2024, 10:00 (Czwartek)

Dodaj do kalendarza

Figure 12 Offshore2Hydrogen

#12

Title: *EduOffshoreWind*

Date: 5-6.03.2024

Location: *Gdańsk*

Participation and/or organization: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel + workshop*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://eduoffshorewind.pl/>

ZARAŻAMY PASJĄ DO ZIELONEJ ENERGETYKI

2. edukacyjne targi kariery

EDU OFFSHORE WIND

5-6 marca 2024, hala AmberExpo, Gdańsk

Innowacyjne kierunki rozwoju kariery zawodowej dla uczniów szkół ponadpodstawowych i studentów.

EDU OFFSHORE WIND 2024 to jedyne w skali kraju wydarzenie, które przybliży rozwojowy rynek pracy w zielonej energetyce w Polsce.

2. edycja **EDU OFFSHORE WIND** to **120** wystawców z innowacyjnej branży zielonej energetyki i **prawie 9000** młodych ludzi odwiedzających targi.

Młodzież szkolna brała udział w kontynuacji programu edukacyjnego,

Figure 13 EduOffshoreWind

#13

Title: *H2Poland*

Date : 24-25.04.2024

Location: *Poznań*

Participation and/or organization: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://h2poland.com.pl/pl/>

Figure 14 H2Poland

#14

Title: *WEBINAR: INWESTYCJE WODOROWE – POTENCJAŁ A WYZWANIA (WEBINAR: HYDROGEN INVESTMENTS – POTENTIAL AND CHALLENGES)*

Date: 01.02.2024

Location: *Online*

Participation and/or organization: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://klasterwodorowy.pl/webinar-inwestycje-wodorowe-potencjal-a-wyzwania,289.pl>

WEBINAR: HYDROGEN INVESTMENTS – POTENTIAL VS. CHALLENGES

BUREAU VERITAS FREE WEBINAR II 01.02.2024 II TIME: 10:00 – 11:00

How to effectively integrate the potential of hydrogen technology while overcoming technological and financial challenges?

Hydrogen technologies attract with their zero emissions, the ability to obtain energy from water, sun and wind. Hydrogen, which has aroused interest for hundreds of years, is becoming an inspiration for today's projects, especially in the face of climate problems. Today, we have returned to proven electrolysis processes, using increasingly modern technological solutions that increase both process safety and the diversity of energy sources.

REGISTER

Despite these advances, we continue to face challenges such as the right choice of technology, adaptation to the legal framework and optimal use of production resources. In our webinar, you will discover both the positive aspects and the challenges of hydrogen technology. We will debunk a few myths and present further steps that are worth taking in the context of the implementation of projects based on hydrogen technology.

TABLE DISCUSSIONS:

- Preparation of the investment – milestones, timeline, basics of economics,
- Technologies for the production, storage and management of hydrogen,
- Supply chains – the level of commercialization and market availability of the technology,
- Feed and process water – treatment technologies,
- Safety of use of the installation,
- Hydrogen taxonomy and certification.

Figure 15 WEBINAR: INWESTYCJE WODOROWE – POTENCJAŁ A WYZWANIA

#15

Title: PESA SMART ENERGY FORUM ENEX

Date: 7-8.02.2024

Location: Kielce

Participation and/or organization: Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://psme.org.pl/pesa-smart-nergy-forum-enex-024/>

Countdown Expired!

ZAREJESTRUJ SIĘ

Organizator:

Figure 16 PESA SMART ENERGY FORUM ENEX

#16

Title: *Spotkanie Online | Zaawansowane Materiały dla Rozwoju Technologii Wodorowych (Online Meeting | Advanced Materials for Hydrogen Technology Development)*

Date: 8.03.2024

Location: *Online*

Participation and/or organization: *Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel*

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://nanonet.pl/spotkanie-online-zaawansowane-materialy-dla-rozwoju-technologii-wodorowych/>

Aktualności

Śląski Klaster NANO, KKK oraz Klaster Technologii Wodorowych zapraszają na spotkanie:

Zaawansowane materiały dla rozwoju technologii wodorowych.

08.03.2024
godz. 11:00-12:30

Gdzie?
Online via Microsoft Teams

Spotkanie Online | Zaawansowane Materiały dla Rozwoju Technologii Wodorowych

Figure 17 Spotkanie Online | Zaawansowane Materiały dla Rozwoju Technologii Wodorowych

#17

Title: *Spotkanie online: Kreowanie zrównoważonych rozwiązań dzięki synergii wodoru i zaawansowanych materiałów (Online meeting: Creating sustainable solutions through the synergy of hydrogen and advanced materials)*

Date: 10.05.2024

Location: Online

Participation and/or organization: Organization & Participation – presentation + discussion panel

Partner: RIGP

Web link: <https://nanonet.pl/spotkanie-online-kreowanie-zrownowazonych-rozwiazan-dzieki-synergii-wodoru-i-zaawansowanych-materialow/>

Aktualności

Śląski Klaster NANO, KKK oraz Klaster Technologii Wodorowych zapraszają na spotkanie:

Kreowanie zrównoważonych rozwiązań dzięki synergii wodoru i zaawansowanych materiałów

10.05.2024
godz. 11:00-12:30

Gdzie?
Online via Microsoft Teams

Współorganizator:

Spotkanie Online | Kreowanie zrównoważonych rozwiązań dzięki synergii wodoru i zaawansowanych materiałów

Figure 18 Spotkanie online: Kreowanie zrównoważonych rozwiązań dzięki synergii wodoru i zaawansowanych materiałów

#18

Title: *Professional Meeting on Hydrogen – PMH2*

Date: *8 October 2024*

Location: *Madrid*

Participation and/or organization: *Ariema Energy and Environment S.L.*

Type of action: *Attendance*

Partner: *CNH2*

Web link: <https://pmh2.com/>

Figure 19 Professional Meeting on Hydrogen – PMH2

2.1.2 Fairs & Exhibitions:

#1

Title: *POLLUTEC 2023, Lyon (France) - stand by ENVI*

Date: *October 2023*

Location: *Lyon (France)*

Participation and/or organization: *POLLUTEC*

Type of Action: *ENVI stand at POLLUTEC with promotion of hydrogen project as HYPOP (flyers, slide about the project)*

Partner: *ENVI*

Figure 20 POLLUTEK 2023

2.1.3 Stakeholders Engagement Activities

#1

Title: ENVI H2 DAY

Date: 26 October 2023

Location: ENVI PARK, Turin

Participation and/or organization: ENVI

Type of Action: H2 DAY event organised by ENVI with support of different projects (synergy with EVERYWH2ERE, BEST4Hy, Sistema Poli – local companies clusters); HYPOP was mentioned several times to emphasise the social acceptance topic. Value chain representatives.

Target reached: Manufacturers/Hydrogen sector; Policy makers, EU and local projects; Clusters, territorial associations, networks, hydrogen valley; Eu and local projects; scientific community

Partner: ENVI

Web link: www.envipark.com/envi-news/idrogeno-e-sostenibilita-in-envipark-vi-aspettiamo-il-26-ottobre-per-lh2day/

Figure 21 ENVI H2 DAY

#2

Title: ANIMA GET IDROGENO

Date: 18 January 2024

Location: On line event

Participation and/or organization: ANIMA IDROGENO ASSOCIATION

Target: Companies, sector experts

Type of Action: HYPOP presentation and invitation to participate to the WP2 for data collection.

Event closed to the ANIMA IDROGENO members.

Partner: ENVI

The screenshot shows a Zoom meeting interface. On the left, a presentation slide titled 'HYDROGEN AREA' is displayed. The slide contains text in Italian and a table with project details. The text states: 'Dal 2002 il Parco Tecnologico offre servizi nel settore dell'idrogeno e delle celle a combustibile, attraverso un laboratorio dedicato in grado di fornire test e servizi di supporto a diversi stakeholder: dal 2019 la struttura del laboratorio è gestita in partnership con il Politecnico di Torino.' The table lists various projects with columns for Title, Starting Year, Application, and Sponsor Role. Below the table, it says 'Project HYPOP - GA n. 10111933'. To the right of the text is a diagram showing the hydrogen value chain: 'From the laboratory to the region. We have the infrastructure, expertise and network to exploit the potential of hydrogen and tackle its challenges.' The diagram includes icons for Research, Hydrogen on-fleet applications, Training and demonstration, Cooperation with stakeholders, and Feasibility studies and assessments. It also shows a flow from 'Energy from renewables' to 'Production' to 'Storage and distribution' to 'End uses'. At the bottom of the slide are logos for 'Clean Hydrogen Partnership' and 'Co-funded by the European Union'. On the right side of the screenshot, a grid of Zoom participants is visible, including Mattia Envispark, Valentina D'Acunti, Paola Capellini, kim fumagalli, Andrea Cuppone, and Marilena Franchino.

TITLE	STARTING YEAR	APPLICATION	SPONSOR ROLE
HYPROFESSIONALS	2020	TRAINING	COURSE DEVELOPMENT, TRAINING INITIALLY
HTUP	2020	BACKUP POWER SUPPLY	TESTING
ELIMABACK	2022	BACKUP POWER SUPPLY	TESTING
ENEFIELD	2022	STATIONARY COP	STAKEHOLDERS ANALYSIS
KNOWHY	2022	TRAINING	COURSE DEVELOPMENT, TRAINING INITIALLY
HYTECHCYCLING	2022	CROSS CUTTING FOCUSED	NORMATIVE ANALYSIS, STAKEHOLDERS ENGAGEMENT
BIOBOROUGH	2022	Advanced direct boron fuel processor for hydrogen production	Third party of ACEA, TESTING in partnership
EVERYWHERE	2022	PORTABLE SENSETS	TEST, LADDER OF DEMONSTRATION
REFLEX	2022	H-SDC	DEMO SITE, TEST ACTIVITY
HyCARE	2022	Hydrogen Cluster for Renewable Energy Storage	Third party of JH2TO on demonstration
BESTLHY	2022	RECOVERY OF CRITICAL RAW MATERIALS	COORDINATOR

Figure 22 ANIMA GET IDROGENO

#3

Conference: Hyvolution Paris 2024

Title: European connection during the event (Discussion with France Hydrogen, Hydrogen Europe and industrial players)

Date: 30/1, 31/1 and 1/3/2024

Location: Paris

Partner: CLUSTER TWEED

Web link: <https://paris.hyvolution.com/fr/les-conferences-hyvolution-paris-2024>

Figure 23 HYVOLUTION PARIS

#4

Conference: Stakeholders engagement during the World Hydrogen Summit

Title: *European connection during the event (MoU with Germany and Nederland)*

Date: 13/05/2024

Location: Rotterdam

Partner: CLUSTER TWEED

Web link: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7195780245860274176>

Figure 24 World Hydrogen Summit

#5

Event: Site Visit with presentations of hydrogen private actors

Title: *Mutual learning exercise on Industrial Decarbonisation.*

Date : 9 April 2024

Location : CRM, Liège, Belgique

Participation and/or organization: *Organization in partenariat with the CRM group*

Partner: CLUSTER TWEED

Web link: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7184505222801543168>

Figure 25 isit at Cluster Tweed, meeting with European Public actors

#6

Webinar

Title: *Whats up in ... Alpin Region concerning hydrogen valleys*

Date: 16/05/2024

Location: *Online*

Partner: CLUSTER TWEED

Web link: <https://clusters.wallonie.be/tweed/fr/news/whatsapp-alpine-region-concerning-hydrogen-valleys-16-mai-2024>

WhatsUp In ... 16 mai 2024 • 11h00-12h30 **Webinars**

Alpine Region concerning Hydrogen Valleys

H2[hub] valley HYPOP Cluster Tweed

Connecting European hydrogen valleys

Estelle Péritel
IMAGHyNE

8 Associated partners

9 Institutional observer group

10 Technical observer group

La Région Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes

The project is supported by the Clean Hydrogen Partnership and its members.

Co-funded by the European Union

Clean Hydrogen Partnership

Figure 26 Whats up in ... Alpin Region concerning hydrogen valleys

#7

EVENTS: CLUSTER TWEED General Assembly

Date: 16/04/2024

Context: 300 people were present for our general assembly. One topic was the vulgarization of the Belgian hydrogen strategy and the explanation of the importance of hydrogen to achieve the energetic transition.

Partner: CLUSTER TWEED

Web link: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7186712084733173760>

Figure 27 CLUSTER TWEED General Assembly

2.1.4 Paper and publication

#1

Conference (submission in M12 and expected participation in M17):

Title (name of the conference): *SETAC Europe 26th LCA Symposium*

Date of the conference: *21-23 October 2024*

Location: *Gothenburg, Sweden*

Participation: *Submission (M12) of the work "Delving into Frameworks for Social Life Cycle Assessment of Hydrogen-Related Products Based on Target Audience" by S.K.R. Maddula, J. Dufour and D. Iribarren*

Partner: *IMDEA*

Web link: <https://www.setac.org/discover-events/topical-events/setac-europe-26th-lca-symposium.html>

#2

Conference: *Powering Net Zero Week*

Date: *3 - 6 December 2024*

Location: *Birmingham*

Participation and/or organization: *The Institution of Engineering and Technology*

Type of action: *Abstracts application - waiting for reply*

Partner: *CNH2*

Web link: <https://poweringnetzero.theiet.org/hydrogen>

Figure 28 Powering Net Zero Week

2.1.5 Public engagement and educational activities

#1

Title: *FABBRICHE APERTE PIEMONTE 2023*

Date: *27-28 October 2023*

Location: *ENVI PARK, Turin*

Participation and/or organization: *ENVI*

Type of Action: *ENVI opens its Park to the citizens: promotion of its activities, HYPOP included. Target Citizens*

Partner: *ENVI*

Web link: <https://www.envipark.com/envi-news/scopri-environment-park-con-fabbriche-aperte-piemonte-2023/>

Figure 29 FABBRICHE APERTE PIEMONTE 2023

#2

Title: EARTH DAY "Stati Generali con i Giovani per la Terra"

Date: 22/04/2024

Location: ENVI PARK, Turin

Participation and/or organization: ENVIPARK, EARTH DAY ITALIA ASSOCIATION

ENVI visit tour and presentation of company activities, included HYPOP project

Web link: <https://www.envipark.com/envi-news/22-aprile-giornata-mondiale-della-terra-gli-appuntamenti-in-envipark/>

Figure 30 EARTH DAY "Stati Generali con i Giovani per la Terra"

#3

Title: University of Castilla-La Mancha students' visit to the CNH2

Date: 20/12/2023, 04/03/2023

Location: CNH2 premises (Puertollano)

Participation and/or organization: CNH2

Description: In these visits, the basics of HYPOP project have been shared with the attendants

#4

Title: Technical visit of the School of Industrial Organisation of Seville (EOI Sevilla)

Date: 30/11/2023

Location: CNH2 premises (Puertollano)

Participation and/or organization: CNH2 and EOI Sevilla

Partner: CNH2

Description: In these visits, the basics of HYPOP project have been shared with the attendants

2.1.6 Social media, website news, newsletter

Activities description: *Introduction to the project in general to spark interest amongst our followers*

Partner: ENVI

Web links:

- www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7165361290301894656
- www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7166115006252625920
- www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7168555860749754368
- www.facebook.com/EnvironmentPark/posts/pfbid02LEA3YCqW7c8669L2VzE5gFKkYGb6e1dqxLnZrHFhrHQhRB3naRhvu14KmhWp5anYI?locale=it_IT
- www.facebook.com/EnvironmentPark/posts/pfbid022wHDF776txCUSBXaC9UGCA3YRQtDH2ixbKa9t1qdNXAUeborCPkUMa3wacxFY5DI?locale=it_IT
- www.facebook.com/EnvironmentPark/posts/pfbid0fTr9jt7FmTbww3V4AMgscRiqJn6syaWJ278ekoaaev1f7A73Wm232dpPzPtrFZ5hl?locale=it_IT
- <https://x.com/HypoPproject/status/1767551126520705443>
- <https://x.com/HypoPproject/status/1756989019840245859>
- <https://x.com/EnvironmentPark/status/1731629283557220738>
- www.facebook.com/permalink.php?story_fbid=pfbid02hs2rdZWXGHMGXxvuZBY3hhqQYaJMDpNGCxEW3LfbJJVBrCFYfbYy18zKhBnynbl&id=61553446107567
- <https://x.com/HypoPproject/status/1756989019840245859>
- <https://x.com/HypoPproject/status/1767551126520705443>
- <https://x.com/HypoPproject/status/1786032909021020557>

Figure 31 Example ENVI post on social media

Activities description: **HYPOP GA Meeting and project presentation**

Partner: **IMI**

Web link:

X: [@IMI_methods](#) | 203 followers

Facebook: [/methodsinnovation](#) | 357 likes, 375 followers

LinkedIn: [/company/methodsinnovation/](#) | 429 followers

Activities description: **HYPOP repost: GA Meeting**

Partner **IMI**

Web link:

Posted to [X](#) (274 views) and [Facebook](#) (3 views)

Figure 32 Example IMI post on social media

Activities description: Invitation to join HYPOP community

Partner: IMI

Web link:

[X](#) (44 views),

[Facebook](#) (25 views, 2 likes)

[LinkedIn](#) (6 reactions, 1 comment, 1 repost)

Figure 33 Example IMI re-post on social media

Activities description: Introduction to the project in general to spark interest amongst our followers

Partner IMI

Web links:

- <https://x.com/HypoPproject/status/1730620851953779125>
- www.facebook.com/methodsinnovation/posts/663954329265290
- https://x.com/IMI_methods/status/1780609065594302792
- www.facebook.com/methodsinnovation/posts/pfbid0uSdCYxYHfTbHhWsh99KiMFjUEoRSie8TbYXhvZGno1W79XqgtyJNbS8tT9VgeiGl
- www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:7186375565266800640

Title: ENVIPARK NEWSLETTER

Date: 18 November 2024

Type of Action: ENVIPARK NEWSLETTER: project launch + link to the website

Web link: www.envipark.com/en/progetti-p/27401-2/

WWW.ENVIPARK.COM

NEWSLETTER ENVIPARK

In questa edizione di novembre, abbiamo selezionato una serie di iniziative e opportunità che riteniamo di maggior interesse. Troverete le principali news sul tema della riqualificazione energetica degli edifici pubblici, materiale di formazione su nuovi modelli di business circolari e corsi di formazioni per esperti in big data e IA e nuovi progetti in partenza.

Tra i prossimi appuntamenti, segnaliamo **RESTRUCTURA**, il salone dell'edilizia e della ristrutturazione che si terrà dal **23 al 25 Novembre** presso il Lingotto Fiere Torino. Ci saremo anche noi con un workshop per i professionisti dell'edilizia in legno.

MENTORING FOR INTERNATIONAL GROWTH: Iscriviti entro il 20 Novembre

AVVISO PUBBLICO DI MANIFESTAZIONE DI INTERESSE per progetti di riqualificazione energetica

25 Novembre, ore 14:00 appuntamento a RESTRUCTURA per parlare di edilizia in legno sostenibile

Follow up da #SME4GREEN con il materiale formativo dal webinar HOW TO FINANCE YOUR SUSTAINABILITY

Dalla cybersecurity e i big data all'Intelligenza artificiale: i corsi MHL per i professionisti del futuro

I NOSTRI PROGETTI

Al via HYPOP, il progetto su opinione pubblica e awareness delle tecnologie a idrogeno
Scopri WOODCIRCLES: soluzioni circolari per l'edilizia sostenibile del legno

Figure 34 ENVIPARK NEWSLETTER

TWEED Newsletter

Title: Our Hydrogen Newsletter

Date: One every 3 months

Context: We publish every three months to our contact members (more than one thousand people) our activity on the hydrogen topics. The HyPOP project has been of course described. For example, our last newsletter is available on this link

Partner: CLUSTER TWEED

Web link: <https://web.apsis.one/preview/19355584-7332-43c0-8608-fe5b2a175256?accountId=cluster-tweed>

• H2Hub Wallonia • Belgian Hydrogen Council •
Rétrospective 2023 et perspectives 2024

A l'instar de ce qui a été fait dans le cadre des communautés d'énergies CERACLE, l'objectif du **H2Hub Wallonia** est de donner une vision transversale sur les principales initiatives H2 en développement en Wallonie et à Bruxelles et de les mettre en synergie.

Début 2023, les clusters régionaux WaterstofNet et Cluster TWEED (H2Hub Wallonia) ont uni leurs forces dans le domaine de l'hydrogène en lançant le **Belgian Hydrogen Council (BHC)** et en réunissant ainsi efficacement l'ensemble de la chaîne de valeur belge de l'hydrogène. Le BHC vise à transcender les différents niveaux politiques de notre pays en conseillant les décideurs politiques sur le déploiement de leurs stratégies régionales et fédérales en matière d'hydrogène.

En même temps, pour soutenir et structurer la recherche en matière d'hydrogène vert, H2Hub a initié le portefeuille **e-WallonHY**, en phase avec la stratégie wallonne S3, et, pour réaliser l'ambition européenne des acteurs wallons, avec le CRM Group.

Les objectifs d'encadrement du **H2Hub Wallonia** sont en phase avec les métiers de **clustering** : susciter l'innovation et l'investissement, catalyser la mise en œuvre des projets sur le marché, fédérer les acteurs, activer les échanges, interfacer les acteurs avec les stakeholders et surtout, valoriser les développements wallons sur le territoire et plus largement en Europe.

Figure 35 CLUSTER TWEED newsletter

Partner: CNH2:

Web link: https://twitter.com/cnh2_es/status/1759539139756556344

Number of post, followers and visualization:

- 2 posts,
- 95 impressions,
- 2 Twitter engagement.

Web

link

"https://www.instagram.com/p/C3hwOLINNVW/?utm_source=ig_web_copy_link&igsh=MzRIODBiNWFZA=="

Number of post, followers and visualization:

- 1 post,
- 122 impressions,
- 3 Instagram engagements

Instagram

Entrar Registrarte

Web link: “https://www.linkedin.com/posts/cnh2-centro-nacional-del-hidr%C3%B3geno-16464211b_hypop-uniaejneuropea-activity-7165302928042311681-oYhJ?utm_source=share&utm_medium=member_desktop”

Number of post, followers and visualization:
 1 post,
 1584 impressions,
 70 LinkedIn engagements.

Publicación de CNH2 - Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno

CNH2 - Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno
 Spanish National Hydrogen Centre
 3 meses

El Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno es una de las entidades participantes del proyecto europeo HYPOP, que busca conocer y mejorar la percepción social del hidrógeno. #HYPOP está financiado por la #UniónEuropea y apoyado por el Clean Hydrogen Partnership y sus miembros.

Os animamos a seguir las redes del proyecto para conocer más y estar al tanto de los avances:

Facebook: HYPOP (<https://lnkd.in/dXtGXmUj>)
 Instagram: @hypoproject (<https://lnkd.in/d3KuJCbV>)
 LinkedIn: HYPOPproject (<https://lnkd.in/dKESnmT>)
 X/Twitter: @hypoproject (<https://lnkd.in/dA9Vmsdz>)
 YouTube: <https://lnkd.in/dyj8ety8>

H + pop + progress + collaboration + water =
 hydrogen inclusive improvement inclusive fuel

HYPOP

Clean Hydrogen Partnership Co-funded by the European Union

45

Web link: “<https://www.facebook.com/CNH2es/posts/pfbid0Lo7CQuUPakw9c1vMHH5YdKfoiUc4ouYYWDyEimhxWNckQGBUkEcDLYyrM9BP621hl>”

Number of post, followers and visualization:
 1 post,
 65 impressions,
 3 Facebook engagements.

facebook

Correo electrónico o teléfono Contraseña [Iniciar sesión](#)

CNH2 - Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno
19 de febrero

El Centro Nacional del Hidrógeno es una de las entidades participantes del proyecto europeo HYPOP, que busca conocer y mejorar la percepción social del hidrógeno. #HYPOP está financiado por la #UniónEuropea y apoyado por el #CleanHydrogenPartnership y sus miembros.

Os animamos a seguir las redes del proyecto para conocer más y estar al tanto de los avances:

Facebook: HYPOP (<https://www.facebook.com/profile.php?id=61553446107567...>)
Instagram: @hypopproject (<https://www.instagram.com/hypopproject/>)
LinkedIn: HYPOPproject (<https://www.linkedin.com/company/100300051/admin/feed/posts/>)
X/Twitter: @hypopproject (<https://twitter.com/HypoPproject>)
YouTube: <https://www.hypop-project.eu/mission/>

3

2.2 KPI Monitoring

The following table, coming from D5.6 – Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan, reports C&D project’s KPI updated at M12:

Table 1 C&D project’s KPI

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
1	HYPOP’s visual identity and related promotional	<p>N. of brand identity kit released: 1</p> <p>N. of social media banners: 2</p> <p>N. of flyers: 2</p> <p>N. of roll-ups: 2</p> <p>N. of informative posters >2</p> <p>N. of flyers distributed >2000</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>	All materials developed
2	Design infographics and develop informative videos	<p>N. of informative videos to explain hydrogen and its application translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >3</p> <p>N. of infographics to visualise project’s outputs translated in 5 languages (incl. English): >5</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>	Ongoing, videos and infographics will be developed and published in Y2
3	Website and social media accounts (LinkedIn, X, Instagram)	<p><u>Website:</u></p> <p>N. of website online (M4): 1</p> <p>N. of total visits: > 15.000</p> <p>N. of countries reached >27</p> <p><u>Social media:</u></p> <p>N. of accounts setup and active (M6): 4</p> <p>N. of posts per year (total): >50</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>	<p>Website online since M4, website visits around 1.500 from 12 countries.</p> <p>Social Media accounts set up (LinkedIn, X, Facebook, Instagram), 36 posts shared on each social media account.</p> <p>Social media campaigns will be</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
		<p>N. of social media campaigns: >5</p> <p><u>N. of LinkedIn//X followers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 700</p> <p>Y2: n° 1000</p> <p><u>N. of Instagram followers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 1000</p> <p>Y2: n° 500</p> <p><u>YouTube viewers:</u></p> <p>Y1: n° 300</p> <p>Y2: n° 600</p> <p>N. of general local event per country participated by the local partner): >1</p> <p>N. of article/radio or tv interviews in national or regional media by local partners for each partner country: >1</p>		<p>implemented in Y2.</p> <p>LinkedIn followers: 255 followers in Y1</p> <p>Instagram followers: 133 followers</p> <p>YouTube followers: 5, no video in the channel yet</p> <p>Events KPI achieved, article under monitoring.</p>
4	Participation in external events and conferences and promotion through traditional media channels (*)	<p>N. of participation in events with dedicated booths: >3</p> <p>N. of speeches at events and conferences (live and online): >5</p>	<p>Scientific experts,</p> <p>Industry, social partners, businesses,</p>	<p>Press Releases are planned in Year 2.</p> <p>Some events have been identified: the EU Hydrogen Week,</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
		<p>N. of articles in newspapers, magazines or radio: >8</p> <p>N. of press releases (to 10.000 + contacts): >6</p>	<p>policy makers, community at large</p>	<p>November 2024; the Sustainable Places Conference, September 2024. Other events will be identified in each country and the best option selected in order to reach the target.</p> <p>Some magazines have been identified for articles production. WP1&WP2 results will be mainly reported with engagement activities planned in Year 2.</p>
5	Joint activities with other initiatives and networks	<p>N. of joint activities (expert meetings): 1</p> <p>N. of mutual learning workshop: >1</p> <p>N. of online meetings with Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory: >3</p> <p>N. of online meetings with EU Clean Hydrogen Mission: >3</p>	<p>Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large</p>	<p>1 meeting with Fuel Cells & Hydrogen Observatory done.</p> <p>1 meeting/synergic activities planned with H2IT - Italian Hydrogen Association to support public and stakeholders engagement.</p> <p>The activities in this part of the table are specified in D5.4.</p>

#	KPI	Target	Audience	Status at M12
6	Interconnection with hydrogen demo-project	N. of joint activities, demonstration event: 4	Scientific experts, Industry, social partners, businesses, policy makers, community at large	The activities in this part of the table are specified in D5.4.

3 Conclusion

This document illustrates the HYPOP's Partners Communication and Dissemination Activities performed during the first 12 months. Some KPI (chapter 3) need to be monitored in order to boost other actions and reach the planned targets, as already described in the strategy of D5.6.

A final and exhaustive report will be then delivered at the end of the project, summarising all communication, dissemination and awareness activities of HYPOP (M24).

4 References

General Reference:

- GRANT AGREEMENT - Project: 101111933 – HYPOP – HORIZON-JTI-CLEANH2-2022-2, 12/05/2023
- CONSORTIUM AGREEMENT - rev. 0, 13/03/2023
- D5.1 First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan - M3
- D5.4 - Networking with other projects and initiatives Report - M12
- D5.6 - First Strategic Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan - M12

 www.hypop-project.eu

 info@hypop-project.eu

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